

Correlation of Bio-Markers (Procalcitonin and CRP) and Platelet Count -A Retrospective Analysis of Dengue and Scrub Typhus Co-Infection for Early Suspicion in Tertiary Care Centres in Rajasthan

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INTRODUCTION

Dengue fever is caused by single-stranded RNA viruses of the genus *Flavivirus*, transmitted by the bite of the infected *Aedes* mosquito, and is considered an endemic disease in the Indian subcontinent^[1]. Dengue fever and scrub typhus are two infections common in tropical countries. They share several demographic, clinical, and laboratory features. While scrub typhus is a potentially life-threatening mite-borne infection caused by the bacterium *Orientia tsutsugamushi*, dengue is a mosquito-borne arbovirus infection transmitted by the bite of *Aedes aegypti*^[2,3]. Both infections are prevalent individually, but cases of coinfection still consider rare^[4]. Coinfection with scrub typhus is rare with dengue. If left untreated, it adversely affects the outcome. The key to diagnosing such coinfections includes a high index of suspicion, repeated clinical examination, and the knowledge of local endemicity^[5]. A high index of suspicion should be present in endemic areas such as Tamil Nadu and Puducherry for dengue and scrub typhus coinfection to facilitate appropriate antibiotics for scrub typhus at the earliest to prevent morbidity and mortality^[6]. The coinfection possibility should be suspected early because delay in diagnosis can lead to longer hospital stay, increased chances of end-organ dysfunction, and mortality^[7].

Several small studies have attempted to identify biomarkers for dengue that will be cost-effective in resource-limited settings^[8]. Recent evidence suggests that markers of inflammation may be useful as biomarkers. Studies have shown higher levels of C-reactive protein (CRP) in severe dengue versus non-severe dengue, with a CRP cutoff level of 30.1 mg/L^[9]. Higher levels of CRP have also been found in patients with dengue compared to other viral illnesses^[10]. Procalcitonin (PCT) is an immunologically active protein, induced through different steps of activation during bacterial infections. It has been shown as a good marker for the diagnosis, severity assessment and outcome prediction, particularly in patients with bacterial infection^[11]. PCT is now recognized as a good biomarker to guide the starting and stopping of antibiotics in the ICU^[12]. Although C-reactive protein (CRP) and procalcitonin (PCT) are widely used inflammatory markers for infectious diseases, their role and potential application for dengue and

scrub coinfection were rarely studied, as high degree of suspicion has to be made for coinfection in a patient presenting with febrile illness with thrombocytopenia and deranged laboratory parameters in post-monsoon season in endemic regions in India. We aimed to conduct a study to assess correlation of bio-markers (procalcitonin AND CRP) and platelet count -a retrospective analysis of dengue and scrub typhus co-infection for early suspicion in two tertiary care centres ICU in Rajasthan.

METHODS

A retrospective hospital-based, cross-sectional study was done in the department of critical care of two tertiary care centres in Jaipur (Apex Hospital, Malviya Nagar Jaipur and Soni hospital, MD road, Jaipur) in Rajasthan, after getting clearance from the Institution Review Board and Institutional Ethics Committee. We reviewed medical records from May 2023 to December 2024 for concomitant diagnosis of dengue fever and scrub typhus.

The case files of eligible patients were audited for demographic details, clinical features, course in the hospital, and diagnosis. The details of laboratory and radiological investigations, coinfections, and line of management were also noted. The patients thus selected were categorised as co-infection (if they demonstrated positivity of both dengue and scrub typhus infectious aetiology as outlined above), else as mono-infection dengue fever or scrub typhus according to the investigation results.

Inclusion criteria: Patients who had ELISA reported scrub typhus among those diagnosed with dengue fever (NS1Ag or IgM ELISA positivity) during May 2023–Dec.2024.

Exclusion criteria: Medical records with incomplete data were excluded from the study.

Twenty-eight records were identified with this combined diagnosis. ELISA for IgM antibodies to *Orientia tsutsugamushi* (*O. tsutsugamushi*) was done in these cases. Among them 8 cases lacked complete clinical and laboratory details. Finally, 20 cases of dengue -scrub typhus co-infection fitted the criteria of inclusion for the analysis. In all these cases, dengue fever had been confirmed by a positive test for Non-structural 1 (NS1) antigen (J Mitra & Co, New Delhi) with or without IgM antibodies to the virus. Scrub typhus had been diagnosed based on compatible clinico-laboratory features and a positive test for IgM antibodies to *Orientia tsutsugamushi* by ELISA (Pan Bio-USA). The cut off had been calculated based on the standard curve for the kit determined by the Receiver Operative Characteristic (ROC) curves obtained from testing sera of three groups of individuals. The clinical protocol was fever, with or without an eschar, respiratory involvement in the form of pneumonitis and a strong history of outdoor activities in the recent past.

Sixty patients, age and gender-matched with a diagnosis of isolated dengue fever were also analysed. Clinical characteristics including duration of fever, headache, presence of rash, arthralgia and organomegaly were noted. Laboratory findings such as blood counts, liver functions, renal functions and coagulation profile were also determined. Serial blood counts were available in all cases till discharge and these were used to identify lowest platelet count and time to attainment of nadir count. Other investigation results were collected based on tests ordered at or within 24 hours of admission.

Similarly, clinical and laboratory characteristics of another sixty age and gender matched individuals diagnosed with isolated scrub typhus were also determined. These were compared with patients having dengue-scrub typhus co-infection.

In the presence of consistent clinical features, dengue was diagnosed by positive IgM serology (rapid card test, SD Biotec; sensitivity 94.2 %, specificity 96.4 %) and scrub typhus by positive IgM enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) (In Bios International, Inc., USA; sensitivity 99 %, specificity 97.5 %). All tests were performed in a

National Accreditation Board of Laboratories (NABL)-accredited lab with stringent protocol-based quality control. Those without an aetiological diagnosis were excluded from the study.

All the samples were transferred on dry ice to laboratory for CRP and it was measured on these stored samples at two time points: enrolment sample (illness day 1) and follow-up (day 5) using the same commercial assay according to the manufacturer's specifications (magnetic bead panel, cat. no. HCVD3MAG-67 K, Merck, Millipore, UK) on a Luminex 200 analyser.

PCT was measured using an electrochemiluminescence method (Elecsys BRAHMS PCT, Roche Diagnostic, Mannheim, Germany) according to the manufacturer's instructions using a Cobas e 411 immunoassay analyser (Roche Diagnostic, Mannheim, Germany). The detection limit for the PCT assay was 0.02 ng/ml. The coefficients of variation for low and high concentrations were 1.7% and 1.4%, respectively.

Data collection and analysis

Clinical information including the duration of fever, associated symptoms (nausea, vomiting, headache, loose stools, breathlessness, abdominal pain, bleeding manifestations and the site of bleed, if present, seizures, unconsciousness, oliguria and swelling over the body etc.) and signs (heart rate, blood pressure, respiratory rate, oxygen saturation, palpable organomegaly and other abnormal clinical findings) was collected at the time of presentation in the hospital for all patients included in the study. Demographic details including age, gender and occupation were also collected and compiled. The haematological and biochemical investigations carried out at the time of hospitalisation were also noted.

Data analysis

Data were analysed using the statistical software SPSS version 22. Qualitative data were presented in the form of frequency and percentage; quantitative data were presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). It was observed that the data were not normally distributed, so median and inter-quartile values (IQR) were calculated. The Kruskal–Wallis H test was used to compare the difference among groups, followed by the Mann–Whitney U test to compute the differences between the groups. A p -value < 0.05 was considered as being statistically significant.

RESULTS

During the period between May 2023 and December 2024, there were 20 cases with a confirmed diagnosis of dengue and scrub typhus co-infection (**Table-1**). The mean age of the patients was 38.1 years, and 70% were males. Abdominal pain was the most common symptom apart from headache. Fever was present in all patients at admission and median duration of fever at the time of admission was 5.0 days. Arthralgia was seen in a significant number of patients (25%). Hepatosplenomegaly was uncommon (**Table 2**). The mean haemoglobin of the patients was 12.8 g/dL. Only two patients had elevated total leukocyte counts, whereas all others had normal counts or leucopenia. The drop in platelet counts during illness was most marked in isolated dengue as compared to co-infection and was significantly lower compared to those with isolated scrub typhus (in coinfection-the median lowest (nadir) platelet count was 29.5×10^9 cells/L). Liver functions revealed transaminitis in all patients, and elevation of AST and ALT was more than three times the upper limit of normal in 94% of patients. AST/ALT ratio was more than one in all patients (**Table-1**).

Comparison of clinical and laboratory parameters:

Patients with co-infection, we did not observe any difference in this sub-group of co-infection in the mean haemoglobin or platelet counts when compared with the mono-infections. Aspartate aminotransferase (AST) and alanine aminotransferase (ALT) were considerably higher in the co-infection group and isolated dengue fever as

compared to isolated scrub typhus (Table 2). The serum bilirubin levels were significantly higher in isolated scrub typhus as compared and co-infection (2.4 vs 1.1 p < 0.001) but not with isolated dengue (1.1 vs 0.8 g/dl; p = 0.75). Serum creatinine and alkaline phosphatase were significantly higher in isolated scrub typhus as compared to isolated dengue or co-infection group. All twenty patients with co-infection received doxycycline. All were started on antibiotics after the results of IgM for scrub were available based on clinical suspicion. All of them responded within 72 hours of antibiotic initiation with temperature touching baseline.

In patients with co-infection, mean of CRP level on day 1st was 50 ± 11.6 mg/L (quartile-19.4/38.4/67.8) was significantly higher than isolated dengue, (mean-30 ± 9.4 -quartile10.4/24.3/41) and scrub typhus (mean-18.2 ±13.4 -quartile-6.2/12.4/31.2) -(Table-2).

The PCT level was significantly higher in co-infection group on day 1st (Mean -1.67 ± 1.78, Quartiles -0.5/1.12/1.3) as compared to isolate dengue (Mean -0.08 ± 0.26, Quartiles -0.04/0.11/0.19) isolated scrub typhus (Mean -1.07 ± 1.45, Quartiles -0.42/1.01/1.15).

Parameters		D + S	Dengue	Scrub typhus
		n = 20	n =60	n = 60
Age (years)	Mean ± SD	38.1 ± 12.5	36.9 ± 14.9	33.9 ± 12.3
	Quartiles (I/II/III)	30/35/48.5	23/35/47	24/32/42
	Range	18–61	18–70	18–65
Sex	Male/female	14.0/7	38/22	42/18
Duration of fever (days)	Mean ± SD	6.9 ± 4.6	5.4 ± 2.2	8.5 ± 3.7
	Quartiles (I/II/III)	4/5/9.5	5/5/6.1	6/8/10.2
	Range	1–20	2–14	3–14
Haemoglobin (gm/dl)	Mean ± SD	12.8 ± 2.5 ^a	13.3 ± 2.3	11.1 ± 1.8
	Quartiles (I/II/III)	11.1/13.1/14.3	12.0/13.2/15.0	9.8/11.0/12.1
	Range	6.4–16.8	7.3–18	6.9–16.3
TLC (×10 ³ /cu.mm)	Mean ± SD	8.3 ± 4.9	6.7 ± 5.3	9.9 ± 4.8
	Quartiles (I/II/III)	4.4/7.4/10.7	3.4/4.8/8.3	6.2/8.3/12.5
	Range	2.2–20.7	1.6–28.7	4.1–23.2
PLT (×10 ³ /cu.mm)	Mean ± SD	87.2 ± 78.5	57.2 ± 53.1	97.9 ± 69.2
	Quartiles (I/II/III)	29.5/54/136.5	18/30/80	50/87/119
	Range	18–309	8.0–258.0	19.0–581.0
AST (IU/l)	Mean ± SD	431.1 ± 1151.9	463.4 ± 1307.2	163.8 ± 136.4
	Quartiles (I/II/III)	54/106/224	90/127/191.5	78/122/192
	Range	20–5326	38–8501	22–679

ALT (IU/l)	Mean ± SD	163.1 ± 347.7	194.5 ± 404.9	105.3 ± 87.7
	Quartiles (I/II/III)	47.5/62/103.5	47.5/72/117.2	51.5/93/116.5
	Range	26–1603	27–2437	19–581
BIL (mg/dl)	Mean ± SD	1.1 ± 1.1 ^c	0.8 ± 0.7	2.4 ± 3.9
	Quartiles (I/II/III)	0.7/0.8/1.1	0.4/0.6/1.0	0.7/1.1/2.7
	Range	0.1–5.9	0.3–4.3	0.5–29.6
AST/ALT	Mean ± SD	1.9 ± 0.9	1.9 ± 0.9 ^c	1.6 ± 0.7
	Quartiles (I/II/III)	1.2/1.7/2.5	1.3/1.7/2.2	1.1/1.5/1.8
	Range	0.3–3.8	0.4–5.4	0.5–4.3
Creatinine (mg/dl)	Mean ± SD	1.1 ± 0.5 ^c	1.0 ± 0.9	1.9 ± 1.8
	Quartiles (I/II/III)	0.8/1/1.5	0.6/0.8/0.9	0.9/1.1/2.5
	Range	0.6–2.6	0.5–5.4	0.5–8.9
ALP (IU/l)	Mean ± SD	154.1 ± 178.7 ^a	81.2 ± 29.8 ^c	401.2 ± 349.5
	Quartiles (I/II/III)	60.7/89.5/154.2	65/71.5/90.7	156.7/274.0/561.2
	Range	52–784	39–181	69–1655
C R P-DAY 1- (mg/L)	Mean ± SD	50 ± 11.6	30 ± 9.4	18.2 ± 13.4
	Quartiles (I/II/III)	19.4/38.4/67.8	10.4/24.3/41	6.2/12.4/31.2
	Range	12.4-97.6	6.4-52	5.4-39
CRP-DAY-5- (mg/L)	Mean ± SD	38 ± 8.9	21 ± 6.4	9.2 ± 2.4
	Quartiles (I/II/III)	13.8/32.4/58.8	7.4/18.4/28.2	4.4/8.4/16.3
	Range	11.9-71	4.3-34	4.1-18
PROCALCITONIN -DAY1-(ng/mL)	Mean ± SD	1.67 ± 1.78	0.08 ± 0.26	1.07 ± 1.45
	Quartiles (I/II/III)	0.5/1.12/1.3	0.04/0.11/0.19	0.42/1.01/1.15
	Range	0.41-1.82	0.03-0.21	0.34-1.35
PROCALCITONIN -DAY-5-(ng/mL)	Mean ± SD	1.39 ± 1.56	0.06 ± 0.16	0.29 ± 0.98
	Quartiles (I/II/III)	0.3/1.03/1.17	0.03/0.10/0.14	0.22/0.51/1.15
	Range	0.38-1.32	0.01-0.19	0.24-1.09
Quartiles (I/II (median)/III); D = dengue, S = scrub typhus				

Significantly different: a from scrub typhus, , b from dengue (Mann–Whitney U test; $p < 0.05$)

Table-2 Clinical characteristics of patients with dengue-scrub typhus co-

	D + S	Dengue	Scrub typhus
	n = 20	n = 60	n = 60
Bleeding	3 (15)	6 (10)	6 (10)
Nausea	3 (15)	4 (6.66)	7 (11.7)
Vomiting	3 (15)	10 (16)	20 (33)
Oliguria	2 (10)	5 (8)	5 (8)
Abdomen pain	5 (25)	19 (31.7)	21 (35)
Malaise	4 (20)	15 (25.0)	10 (16)
Headache	4 (20)	11 (18.3)	10 (16)
Loose stools	1 (5)	3 (5.0)	7 (11.7)
Breathlessness	4 (20)	4 (6.66)	19 (31.7)
Hepatomegaly	3 (15)	5 (8.0)	20 (33)
Splenomegaly	0 (0)	1 (1.7)	11 (18.3)
arthralgia	5(25)	6(10)	7(11.7)
The figures in parentheses are percentages			

DISCUSSION

Positive serology for dengue and/or scrub typhus infection with/without positive malarial smear (designated as mixed or co-infection) is being increasingly observed during epidemics of acute undifferentiated febrile illnesses (AUFIs) ^[12]. Due to overlapping clinical features, scrub typhus infection may be missed in presence of dengue. Concurrent infection with those two pathogens is rare and creates a diagnostic dilemma ^[6]. We describe the clinical and laboratory features of patients diagnosed with this rare combination of infections and compare with those of patients with isolated dengue fever and isolated scrub typhus. Early detection of scrub-typhus in dengue remains challenging. Serological markers like CRP and procalcitonin (PCT) may be used for this role, but it needs to be investigated. We evaluated the performance of CRP and PCT for early detection of scrub coinfection in patients with dengue admitted to the tertiary care centres in Rajasthan.

Duration of fever, mean age of presentation and male to female ratio in our study were similar to the study by Ahmed et al ^[12]. A higher pulse rate and lower systolic blood pressure were findings that suggested co-infection

whereas other clinical findings differed little between patients with co infection and those with dengue fever. Co-infections appeared to reduce the occurrence of clinical features like hepato-splenomegaly seen with mono-infections of dengue and scrub typhus ($p < 0.05$). Even organ dysfunction was significantly less in terms of the number, severity and progression of organ dysfunction in the co-infection group as compared to mono-infections, correlating with the study of Ahmed et al [12].

Thrombocytopenia is typically associated with dengue fever but has also been reported in cases of scrub typhus [13,14]. In this study, we found thrombocytopenia in all three groups. Platelet count was found to be lower in patients with isolated dengue as compared to those with co-infection but it was significantly lower than isolated scrub typhus ($p < 0.05$). Thrombocytopenia in both infections is believed to be immune mediated; hence, co-infected patients probably had synergistic immune suppression of platelets leading to lower platelet counts.

Existing WHO criteria for dengue with warning signs rely heavily on clinical examination findings, with the inclusion of changes in haematocrit and platelet count representing the only laboratory markers of anticipated severity. However, while the importance of these parameters has been emphasized by recent studies [15,16], our findings suggest that the approach to risk stratification could be further refined with the inclusion of baseline CRP. The prognostic potential of markers of generalized inflammation has previously been suggested, in view of the known immune-enhancing effect inherent to dengue's pathogenicity with scrub typhus [17,18]. However, recent investigation into the association between CRP and severity of disease has yielded conflicting results, our findings are consistent with Vuong showing higher levels of CRP during coinfection versus isolated dengue or isolated scrub as increased CRP levels in the first 3 days of illness are associated with worse dengue clinical outcomes [19]. Other studies have shown a lower range of CRP in dengue infection, but this variability is likely reflective of heterogeneity in laboratory methods used, timing of serum sampling, and classification of clinical outcome. Importantly, each study reporting an absence of association between CRP and severity of disease focused on measures of CRP taken later than 3 days into the course of illness, which may account for their disagreement with our results.

There is positive correlation between serum PCT level and the severity of scrub typhus, and serum PCT level may be a biomarker in assessing the severity of scrub typhus [21]. Serum PCT level was positively correlated with severity of illness in non-sepsis critically ill patients, which had predicted value on prognosis [22]. PCT may be useful in the prognostication of dengue fever where: (1) At a cut-off of >0.3 ng/mL, it predicts severe dengue at a sensitivity level of 73% and specificity of 85% when combined with lethargy and albumin [23]. We did not find any particular study comparing PCT level in coinfection of dengue with scrub versus isolated infection, but these previous studies strengthen our findings of high PCT in coinfections versus isolated infections signifying the role of bio-markers in early suspicion in this rare entity of co-infection.

The major limitation of this study is its retrospective nature. The small number of cases in the specific co-infections was a major limitation in bringing out the differences with the relevant mono-infection, if any. Despite the limitations, the study has been able to bring to light an unrecognized yet significant aetiological group being frequently observed in this part of the world.

CONCLUSION

1. Dengue and scrub typhus co infection may be an under-recognized combination of concurrent infections in the tropics, particularly India.
2. Despite increasing global efforts to reduce the physical and socioeconomic impact of dengue and scrub typhus, reliable biomarkers for predicting disease severity remain scarce.

3. Current management of undifferentiated fever in the rural tropics however is unacceptable, with dire health outcomes from common treatable infections going undiagnosed, while overconsumption of antibiotics contributes to a potential global public health catastrophe.
4. We believe the addition of CRP rapid tests and serum procalcitonin to current syndromic based treatment algorithms could be a feasible, effective, and affordable measure to improve healthcare delivery across the tropics; further work to confirm this approach is warranted.
5. Larger prospective studies are needed to estimate the exact magnitude and impact of this co-infection and role of biomarkers in early diagnosis to prevent morbidity and mortality.

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